

**PERCEPTIONS OF LOOKED-AFTER YOUTHS ON
WEAKNESSES OF PSYCHOSOCIAL SUPPORT
INTERVENTIONS IN CHARITABLE CHILDREN'S
INSTITUTIONS IN UASIN GISHU COUNTY, KENYA**

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Abstract

This study was undertaken to provide insight into the perceptions of looked-after youths on the weaknesses of psychosocial support interventions provided to them in charitable children's institutions. The sample in this mixed approach research consisted of all youths (n=260) in charitable children's institutions which provides both institutional and community type care (practice reintegration) in Uasin Gishu County, Kenya. Data was collected using a Looked-After Youth Questionnaire, an interview schedule and focus group discussions. Measures were appraised by psychology experts before use. Descriptions of qualitative data were made detailed to lend it for transferability. Examination of percentage scores of identified weaknesses of psychosocial support interventions in care homes revealed that poor management of traumatic experience by homes rank highest. This was followed by a lack of basic needs, insufficient youth participation in decision-making processes, and inadequate life skills training for caregivers. Based on the above findings, it is recommended that care-givers be facilitated to acquire capacities to enable them to significantly scale up targeted psychosocial interventions. Specifically, they should be trained on complexity of trauma so as to gain thorough understanding of child system of care and how the same impacts the brain development.

Key Words: Psychosocial support interventions, Charitable children's institutions, Looked-after youths, reintegrated children

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INTRODUCTION

The Kenya Demographic Health Survey 2005/06 indicates that 13.1% of all children who are between 0 and 14 years old reside outside of parental care in Kenya. The latest reports indicate that the numbers of such youths are escalating in Kenya and globally (Sitienei & Pillay, 2019; Gayapersad *et al.*, 2019). According to the Government of Kenya (2014), a fragment of this group of children requires special care and protection due to negative impacts of poverty, abuse or neglect of their lives. Research report that these children experience greater difficulties coping with mental problems compared to other normal people (Richardson & Joughin, 2000), with nearly half of them corresponding with the criteria for a psychiatric condition (Bazalgette, Rahilly & Trevelyan, 2015). These mental health challenges may be managed through a well-planned, professionally staffed and supervised environment that facilitates these types of children's growth out of their traumatic past (Richardson & Lelliott, 2003; National Psychosocial Support Guidelines for Orphans and Vulnerable Children in Kenya [NPSG], 2015).

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Psychosocial support in charitable children's institutions should therefore ideally offer measures to help build children's resilience and overcome psychosocial suffering. This is because, in care home set up, the caregivers are supposed to be well-versed with the requisite psychosocial skills and knowledge to assist looked-after children in rebuilding their mental health upon entry and during their subsequent stay (Miseki, 2018). Moreover, care homes are meant to empower looked-after children's capacities to live independent lives as they prepare to exit care (Muthoni, 2007; Uganda Care Leavers, 2019).

Provision of quality environment in care home is key in order to facilitate proper growth and development of looked after children (NPSG, 2015). It can help reduce the psychological distress that children and young people may experience as a result of facing a range of life difficulties, such as being bullied or experiencing bereavement; support those who are having difficulties within relationships and those who are having difficulty managing their emotions, such as anger. However, this can be possible if children in care get access to sustainable and consistent psychosocial interventions. This then calls for a framework to be in place to guide on nature of care and treatment for children and adolescents with mental illnesses in care environment.

However, there are doubts over the value of psychosocial support given to vulnerable children in care homes in Kenya (Wairire, 2006; Amolo *et al.*, 2012, Waithaka, 2022). This view is augmented by an ongoing debate on whether or not charitable children's institutions spread across the Kenyan counties have the capacity to rebuild young people's lives (Kenya Society of Careleavers and Koinonia Old Beneficiaries Welfare Association, 2013; Miseki, 2018). In Uasin Gishu County, for instance, charitable children's institutions face a lot of challenges such as inadequate funds and facilities, unskilled employees, lack of guidelines on rehabilitation and the increase in the number of children and runaway youths in need of care (Wakhu-Wamunga, 2011). This calls into question their ability to fully respond to needs of children under their care. Therefore, there is a need to evaluate the efficacy of psychosocial support in care homes on the face of these challenges.

Previous research within Kenya has explored the link between orphan hood condition and variables like immunizations, dieting and psychological output (Lee *et al.*, 2014). There is paucity of research targeting the nature of psychosocial services provided to vulnerable children taken into care. No study was found to specifically look at the effectiveness of psychosocial care from the perspective of children themselves.

Purpose of the Research

Psychosocial care in a charitable institution for children is primarily aimed at rebuilding personal competences of children through modifying their behaviour with more desirable behaviours that improve their long-term wellbeing. This is achieved through facilitating children to engage in group activities and peer engagement, which develop their positive social interactions and relationships; providing educational support, problem-solving activities, and intellectual stimulation, which can enhance their intellectual abilities; and addressing emotional needs by providing a caring environment where youth feel free to express their emotions and needs. However, evidence suggests that some looked-after children exit residential care without being prepared to work independently due to a lack of key personality competencies such as resilience. Consequently, Kenya's National Crime Research Centre (2020) has proposed need for stakeholders to establish quality of services provided by persons managing child protection issues in charitable children's institutions in the country. The purpose of this study was to analyse perceptions of looked-

after youths on the weaknesses of psychosocial support interventions provided to them in charitable children's institutions. It was expected that the study would provide information that will be used to develop policy recommendations in reviewing nature of psychosocial programmes in children institutions so as to adequately respond to needs of the looked-after children. Towards this end, answers to the following question were sought: What is the perception of looked-after-children on the nature of psychosocial support services available for them in child care institutions?

1. METHOD

1.1. Design

This study utilized mixed method approach in sourcing for data from the respondents. It specifically employed convergent parallel mixed methods design where the researcher collected both quantitative and qualitative data, analysed them separately, and then compared the results to see if the findings confirmed or disconfirmed to each other (Creswell, 2014). The target population comprised all the looked-after children in charitable children's institutions that provided a combination of residential care and community supports in Uasin Gishu County. Nine care homes were targeted based on above criteria.

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1.2. Sample

Purposive sampling technique was used to get charitable children's institutions to participate in the study. This technique was ideal because it allowed the researcher to select the institutions with the required characteristics of the study (Shaughnessy, Zechmeister & Zechmeister, 2012). Seven of the nine care homes providing both family and residential based care were all selected for the actual study. Additional sampling techniques were then used to get respondents for survey, focus group discussion and in-depth interview.

A census of all the looked-after youth in targeted care homes was possible in this study because their population was small, defined and accessible (O'Leary, 2014). This was done based on records of the children being cared for by the seven purposely selected care homes. Most of these homes were concentrated within Eldoret town (the

headquarters of county of study) which made it easier for the researcher to access and collect data. Census was therefore the second stage in sampling process.

This study conducted two focus group discussions with each group having seven participants. One group was made up of looked-after youth who live in residential care. Each of the seven purposely-selected care homes provided one participant. The second focus group had seven members randomly drawn from those youths living under community model of care. Selection to both groups was done through lottery method. First, the population of the youth in each of the models of care was determined. Each youth was then assigned a number. Numbers corresponding to the number of youth were written on separate slips of paper. Slips were then folded and placed in a hat and mixed thoroughly (this was done separately for youth in the community model of care and those in the residential setting). Seven slips were then randomly drawn from each hat. The students corresponding to the numbers on the drawn slips constituted the FGD sample. The longest serving youth in each of the seven care homes was purposely selected for an in-depth interview. These youths provided insider knowledge on how psychosocial environment of their care homes.

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1.3. Measures

Following receipt of the requisite ethical committee approval, researcher used three instruments to solicit data from the respondents. These were the Looked-After Children Questionnaire, an Interview Guide for Looked-After Youth and the Looked-After Children Focus Group Guideline. The instruments were developed based of the focus of research objectives, hypotheses and related literature. The looked-after youths' questionnaire had open-ended items. The semi-structured questions allowed the respondents to be autonomous and thus provide views and suggestions that are not influenced by researcher's worldview. Semi-structured and open-ended questions were asked on face to face and one to one basis and that stimulated discussions as well as probable explanations to the research questions posed. The focus group interview schedule was regularly redesigned as new ideas emerged during the research progress that captured all relevant aspects of the research

The study used triangulation method of data collection in order to ensure that no essential information was left out. Furthermore, the measures were appraised by four psychology

experts by use of Content Validity Index (CVI). In order to lend the qualitative findings to transferability, efforts were made to make description more detailed to include setting and element of shared experience

1.4. Data Analysis

The respondents were asked to highlight major weaknesses of psychosocial support services in their institution. This was analysed using descriptive statistics (means and standard deviation). Colaizzi's descriptive phenomenological method approach to data analysis (Morrow, Rodriguez & King, 2015) was utilized to identify themes from the interview and focus group data. Themes emerged through repetitively going over the data and noteworthy statements expressed by the youth. Meanings were then formulated in order to identify patterns and recurrent ideas, which were then built into themes. Several adjustments were made to the themes based on youths' feedback. This ensured that the analysis was faithful to the lived experiences of the respondents.

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1.5. Ethical Approval

The research context was primarily within disempowered and stigmatized communities in which there was potential for a perception of an implicit power differential between the charitable children's institutions members and the researcher. Consequently, a number of ethical principles were embedded in the design of this research, training of research assistants, collection and processing of data and finally reporting and dissemination of findings. This research adhered to principles of behaviours that ensured what is legally, morally and culturally acceptable by respondents and government agencies was practised during the course of the research. Approval for the study was granted by the National Commission for Science, Technology and Innovation (Permit No. NACOSTI/P/23353/28675). Following official permission from the County Children Officer, the purpose of the study was explained to the caregivers and respondents meeting the research criteria and consenting to participate.

2. RESULTS

This study was geared towards identifying and evaluating the perceptions of looked-after youths on the weaknesses of psychosocial support interventions in care homes. In order to meet the intent of this objective, the participants were requested to highlight challenges

facing provision of psychosocial support intervention in their care home. The findings and discussion thereof of above-mentioned objective were as presented in the sections below. For ease of analysis and understanding, these specific issues were categorised into broad themes as reported in Table 1.

Table 1: Perceptions of Looked-after Youths on the Weaknesses of Psychosocial Support Interventions in Care Homes

Rank of weaknesses of psychosocial support interventions in care homes	Frequency	Percentage
Poor management of traumatic experiences	39	13.1
Lack of basic needs	34	11.4
Insufficient participation in decision making on issues affecting them	27	9.1
Inadequate life skill training	25	8.4
Lack of persons and environments that inspire hope	21	7.1
Poor caregiver-youth relationship	20	6.7
Poor management of issues in homes	16	5.4
Prevalence of emotional abuse in care environment	15	5.1
Expectation and work load too high in care home	14	4.7
Insufficient training on conflict resolution mechanism	11	3.7
Prevalence of physical abuse in care environment	11	3.7
Caregivers not understanding developmental needs of young people	11	3.7
High population in care home	9	3
Poor counsel from peers	9	3
Lack of assurance on protection from harm	7	2.4
Lack of role models to copy from	6	2
Engrained effects of abuse of drugs and substances a by youths	5	1.7
Inadequate recreational opportunities	5	1.7
Minimal socialization opportunities	5	1.7
Inadequate opportunities to communicate with families	3	1
Uncertainty over care home closure	3	1
Inadequate provision of referral services	1	0.34

Source: Field Data, 2024.

It is discernible from above table that youth in care set up consider mishandling of traumatic experiences by caregivers (13.1%) to be a major weakness of psychological support intervention they receive. Research by Nduku, Mulinge, & Arasa, (2022) concluded that children in orphan institutions of care have a high prevalence of PTSD and other comorbidities mainly anxiety and depression. Care homes should therefore have

capacities to manage these disorders among youth in their rank. However, it is apparent that those charged with helping in managing mental health are either unreachable, unfriendly, disinterested or have little capacities to manage traumatic experiences. According to Shumba and Moyo (2014), if mental health issues of orphans and other vulnerable children are left unattended as if it seems to be care in study area, children will continue experiencing variety of problems like guilt, denial, stigmatization, depression and suicidal ideation. These according to Save the Children UK/SADC (2011) are likely to have negative impact on the child's life in terms of schooling, socialization and making choices in life.

The FGD conducted with reintegrated youth strongly brought out the aspect of mishandling of traumatic experiences by caregivers. This is captured in the extract below.

"...major challenge of psychosocial support services in my case is there is no regular follow up to check on the progress for counselling or guidance offered on the past challenges. Physical follow up is done once in a while especially for those of us who are going to college."

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It is discernible from above that youths who are reintegrated feel left out of psychosocial programmes which many care homes provide to youth under their care. It is probable that their relatives who are in charge of them after reintegration do not have capacity to manage their issues well. There is need for such families, it seems, to be properly trained on ways of handling traumatised looked-after youth before the time comes for them to house and take full charge of them. Such training is key as quantitative findings in this study have shown clearly that significant mental health handicaps among reintegrated youth exist.

Another member of the FGD brought up a different angle to the handling of traumatic experiences as captured in the extract below.

"...most of the individuals who handle our issues are illiterate and lack experience to understand us...they instil fear of consequences which makes some of us to fail to recover from thoughts of difficulties of the past. This brings about stress as the methodology is not suitable"

It is apparent from this extract that care set ups lack staff with the capacity to nurture a therapeutic environment in care set up. A therapeutic environment cannot be achieved if the care home does not have a qualified and a well-motivated staff. In care settings, therefore, there needs to be clarity about the qualifications and role of different cadre of caregivers in delivering the functions of the service within the framework of its defined

mission and vision. The care home manager must be qualified and understand the nature and treatment of trauma in order to provide leadership to staff and ensure that all care practices are safe and appropriate for the child's needs. The total range of care practices in the home should be managed so as to fully support any therapeutic intervention (GoK/UNICEF, 2013).

The next weakness as ranked by the looked after youth is that care homes lack basic services and amenities (11.4%). This scenario could be affecting the youth wellbeing in care homes. This assertion is augmented by one of the youths during FGD with group of youth living in care. This is illustrated in the extract below.

"...our dormitory used to be made out of iron sheets, was very cold at night. Water was a problem too until some well-wishers put up a tank for us. Since we are nowadays many in the institution it is at times difficult to get attention of a mother to listen and act on your challenge."

Above extract point to inadequacy of manpower and vital amenities in some care homes. Such a scenario has potential to further harm mental health of vulnerable youth who are ideally taken in there for purposes of rehabilitation. According to UNICEF (2009), basic services like food, water, healthcare, shelter and security form the first level of support provided to any group of vulnerable children. These provisions form the core of psychological requirement of a group of vulnerable children. Provision of these services according to UNICEF increase positive behaviour among the youth and instil in them a sense of hope for the future. Lack of basic needs and services on the other hand affect children in care disproportionately, as they have no power to reduce their poverty or to mitigate its effects. They are completely reliant on their caregivers for their shelter, nutrition and care. The final effects to individual children people include: poor physical and mental health, stigmatisation, unstable friendships, going without the things that children need, poor educational achievement due to poor cognitive development and poor health and engaging delinquent behaviour and crime (ACCIK, 2015; Madsen, 2016).

It appears from Table 1 that the looked-after youths' voices are not sufficiently heard during planning and execution of programmes in care homes. A sizable percentage (9.19%) feel that the carers hardly consult them on decisions which concern them in the care home. In four of the seven interviews conducted, four highlighted opaqueness of decision making in care set up as a problem. This is captured in the extract below.

“A friend did not want to leave our home to go and stay with the grandmother but our manager had him leave anyway...even now it is hard to make a decision on when you can go visit biological family. I know of friends who become rebellious to counter lack of participation in issues concerning them. They had issues with where to go church, activities of interest and schools to attend and consequently staged some form of resistance like doing tasks late and poorly or just refused to do what they were asked to do.”

Above extract point to negative impact of lack of youth participation in decision making among youth in care. Apart from breeding negativity as alluded in above extract, such practice goes against the united nations principles of supporting children’s voice and free participation in all phases of child protection programming. The United Nations agencies hold that when child participations enhanced it build resiliency which is key in buffering a vulnerable child from adversities. Caregivers should be sensitised on how to play a role of authoritative parent to youth in care by being trained on how to enforce rules and give consequences, but at the same time take the youths’ feelings into considerations (Morin, 2019).

A sizeable number of respondents cited inadequate life skill training (8.4%) as an impediment to psychosocial support interventions in the care set up. There could be value dilemma as homes grapple on the nature of values to teach children most of whom have been raised and thought African based values in their places of birth. Others have lived on streets and are therefore versed with ‘survival for fittest’ kind of lifestyle of the street. Many homes are founded and receive funding from people with links with developed western world countries and as such, these homes are often forced to conform to Eurocentric norms and style of doing things in order to gratify these donors. There is likely to be value dilemma in care set up when all these interests and expectations converge in care set up. This could be so as it is elucidated by a youth in the interview extract below.

“Children get confused and take long to recover from difficulty when the home hold different value system to the one he/she is used to. Value expectations imposed by care homes upon being taken in at times make adjusting to life there more difficult and some sneak back to fend for themselves in an out of care arrangement.”

Value systems vary and caregiver need to balance the systems well in order to make adjustment of youth in care easy and enjoyable. According to Mpofu (2011) indigenous African cultural values revolve around the following values: sense of community life; sense of good human relations; sense of the sacredness of life; sense of hospitality; sense of the sacred and of religion; dynamic and cyclical sense of time and sense of respect for

authority and the elders among others. Dominant Euro-American values, on the other hand, centre on individualism; secularism; a mechanistic, static, ordered worldview (Gichinga, 2007; Mkhize, 2004). There is therefore need for caregivers to be cognizant of these value difference and choose a system that fits the aspiration of the youth. This will likely minimise frustrations among youth, which turn leads to most youth remaining engaged to care programmes.

CONCLUSION

This paper provided insight into the on the weaknesses of psychosocial support interventions provided to looked-after children in institutions of care in Kenya. It was established that youth in care set up consider mishandling of traumatic experiences by caregivers to be a major weakness of psychological support programmes they receive. A sizeable number of youths ranked lack basic services and amenities as a key bottle neck hampering provision of psychosocial support in care set up. In addition, significant number of youths cite insufficient participation in decision making on issues affecting them as a major flaw in quest by caregivers to provide psychosocial support in care set up. One other noteworthy challenge was the perceived inadequate life skill training which significant number of youths consider to be an impediment to psychosocial support interventions in the care set up. finally, it can be concluded that caregivers are not cognizant of value difference in a care set up and often fail to choose a system that fits the aspiration of the youth.

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RECOMMENDATIONS

Owing to inadequate provision of several aspects of both psychological and social care for youth in care set up, caregivers need to be facilitated to acquire capacities to enable them to significantly scale up targeted psychosocial interventions. Of concern is caregivers' apparent lack of know-how on the neurobiology of trauma. They need to be educated on the impact of child abuse and neglect on a child's wellbeing. In addition, they need to be trained on complexity of trauma, and to gain thorough understanding of child system of care and how the same impacts the brain development.

The government agencies that register and regulate running of care homes must strictly enforce the requirement that those tasked with raising children in care set up not only

have basic professional qualification, but also have capacity to provide basic services and amenities

The voices of the youth on how they need to be managed ought to be incorporated into care policies. Incorporating the voices of youth into care policies is vital for creating effective and responsive support systems that truly meet their needs and aspirations

Some youth enter care setting with engrained indigenous values and life skills shaping their worldview of things. Most care homes are run by international volunteers who although working with local based non-governmental entities, could be inadvertently propagating alien values to the youth. In order to minimize domination of Euro-American values in psychosocial provisions, there is need for caregivers to be cognizant of foundational values espoused by the youth under their care and choose provisions that fits the aspiration of the youth.

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